

Supplementary Material

I. REPLICATION STUDY ID-CARD

To support the replication of our study, we created the replication study ID-card composed of 47 questions provided by Abualhajia et al. [1]. Table I shows the replication study ID-card.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Abualhajia, F. B. Aydemir, F. Dalpiaz, D. Dell'Anna, A. Ferrari, X. Franch, and D. Fucci, "Replication in requirements engineering: the nlp for re case," *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 1–33, 2024.

TABLE I

ID-CARD FOR OUR STUDY. THIS ID-CARD IS THE TEMPLATE OF 47 QUESTIONS PROPOSED BY ABUALHAIJA ET AL. [1] TO FOSTER THE REPLICATION OF NLP4RE STUDIES.

Question	Answer
What RE task is your study addressing?	Requirements classification
What types of NLP task is your study tackling?	Classification (choose among classes)
What is the input of your NLP task?	Sentences
What type of classification is the study about?	Binary-single label
What are the labels that can be assigned?	Useless/Helpful
How many data items do you process?	Baseline dataset: 1,000 records; External dataset: 5,068 records
In which year or interval of years was the data produced?	2020 (baseline dataset) and 2015 (external dataset)
What is the source of the data?	User-generated content
What is the level of abstraction of the data (not limited to requirements)?	User-level
What is the format of the data?	User reviews
How rigorous is the format of the data?	Unconstrained natural language
What is the natural language of the data (if applicable)?	English
Please list which domains your data belongs to:	Baseline dataset: Productivity, Social Media, Messaging, and Games; External dataset: Games, Productivity, Travel, Photography, Communication, and Social
How many different sources does your data come from?	Apple App Store and Google Play Store
Is the dataset publicly available (also from other authors)?	Fully (both datasets)
What license has been used?	No license (both datasets)
Where is the dataset stored?	Baseline dataset: in a persistent platform with DOI; External dataset: on GitHub
Provide a URL to the dataset, if available, or to the original paper that proposed the dataset:	Baseline dataset: https://zenodo.org/records/3626185 ; External dataset: https://github.com/mohammadzaem/classification_of_app_reviews
How many annotators have been involved?	603 (baseline dataset) and 10 (external dataset)
How are the entries annotated?	Multiple annotators per entry
What is the average level of application domain experience of the annotators?	None or unknown
Who are the annotators?	Independent annotators
How was the annotation scheme established among the annotators?	Written guidelines with definitions and examples
Did the authors make the written guidelines public?	Yes
Did the authors share other information that could support the annotators other than the elements to annotate?	Surrounding context
Did the authors employ techniques to mitigate fatigue effects during the annotation sessions?	No (not mentioned)
What are the metrics used to measure intercoder reliability?	Baseline dataset: other (precision, recall, and F1); Exnted dataset: not mentioned
How were conflicts resolved?	Baseline dataset: not resolved; External dataset: discussions and third annotator to break the tie
What is the measured agreement?	Not provided
What is the type of proposed solution?	Supervised deep learning and zero-shot GPT-4o classifier
What algorithms are used in the tool?	BERT, ELMo, FastText, and GPT-4o
What has been released?	Source code
What needs to be done for running the tool?	Compile and run
What type of documentation has been provided alongside the tool?	README and environment configuration (requirements.txt) files
What type of dependencies does the tool have?	Open source software/libraries
How is the tool released?	In a persistent platform with DOI
What license has been used?	Reuse for any purpose
Where is the tool released?	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612003
What metrics are used to evaluate the approach(es)?	Precision, Recall, and F1-score
What is the validation procedure?	Train-test split
What baseline do you compare against?	Baselines models
Please provide more details about the baseline you compare against, if any.	For deep learning models: compared against traditional ML models, including SVM and Naive Bayes; For GPT-4o model: compared against supervised deep learning and machine learning models.

*We excluded 6 questions from the template that were not related to the scope of the baseline study.